

Conference Abstract

The distribution of the mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) and the weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in Hungary over the past fifty years and the threats to the persistence of their populations

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Abstract

In the Carpathian Basin, large-scale water regulation projects in the 18th century – primarily the drainage of extensive marshlands – led to a significant reduction in wetland habitats, which in turn caused dramatic declines in the populations of marsh-dwelling fish species. Among these, the mudminnow *Umbra krameri* WALBAUM, 1792 suffered the most severe population decrease. In the 21st century, the few remaining relict populations are increasingly threatened by habitat desiccation due to climate change, the spread of the invasive Amur sleeper *Perccottus glenii* DYBOWSKI, 1877, improper water management practices by water authorities (including dredging operations), and pollution from both agricultural and municipal sources. The Mudminnow is currently classified as “strictly protected” in Hungary. Over the past 30 years, we have attempted to locate surviving populations across the entire country. Unfortunately, the species has completely disappeared from several sites where it was previously known to occur, likely due to recurring droughts and the population boom of the Amur sleeper. Most of the surveys were conducted using low-voltage battery-powered electrofishing equipment, often under difficult field conditions caused by dense submerged and emergent aquatic

vegetation and deep soft sediment. At most sites, photographic documentation of the habitats was taken, and key water quality parameters (pH, dissolved oxygen, conductivity, temperature) were measured. The number of individuals of captured species was recorded using a digital voice recorder. The weatherfish *Misgurnus fossilis* (LINNAEUS, 1758) has shown somewhat better adaptability to the altered, reduced habitats following historical water regulation measures. Stable populations still exist in several drainage channels, old streambeds, and oxbow lakes. The weatherfish is currently classified as “protected” in Hungary. It has persisted in several marshy habitats from which the Mudminnow has completely disappeared. Nevertheless, its populations are also threatened by inappropriate water level regulation, dredging activities, and pollution of agricultural and urban origin. In this presentation, we aim to provide an overview of the distribution of these two protected and endangered marsh-dwelling fish species in Hungary over the past 50 years, and to identify the main threats to the persistence of their populations.

Keywords

ecology, habitat loss, faunistic research, electrofishing, endangered fishes

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.